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BIOLOGICS IN SYNERGY TO DEGRADE TARGET MICROPOLLUTANTS

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About 3500 chemicals have proven eco-toxicological influence¹. Approaches to remove such chemicals or pollutants from the environment may include: (i.) Incineration, but each 1000 kg of waste generally release during incineration 790 kg of carbon into the atmosphere, or about 2.9 tons of CO₂; (ii.) chemical degradation and recycling methods, that are more widely used; and (iii.) biological degradation, recycling and upcycling strategies that have been demonstrated as necessary alternatives. Screening and design novel enzymes plays a pivotal role in advancing our bioremediation strategies for addressing the diverse contamination challenges at environmental sites, ranging from industrial areas to agricultural fields, to wastewater and aquatic ecosystems each with unique pollutant profiles including petroleum hydrocarbons, chlorinated solvents, microplastics², and pharmaceuticals. In this presentation we provide new advances in deciphering degradation networks, and identifying and engineering the corresponding enzymes from multiple genomes and meta-genomes, for multiple contaminants with the goal of revitalizing polluted environments to meet the highest environmental quality standards (Figure 1), contributing significantly to the broader vision of a zero-pollution future and enhanced biodiversity in line with the Natura 2000 network.

Figure 1. Schematic representations of target pollutants for which biocatalytic enzymatic-degradation systems are yet to be fully established.

- [1] Erik Kristiansson, Jessica Coria, Lina Gunnarsson, Mikael Gustavsson. *Environmental Science & Policy* 2021, 126: 90-98
- [2] A. Robles-Martín, R. Amigot-Sánchez, L. Fernandez-Lopez, J. L. Gonzalez-Alfonso, S. Roda, V. Alcolea-Rodriguez, D. Heras-Márquez, D. Almendral, C. Coscolín, F. J. Plou, R. Portela, M. A. Bañares, A. Martínez-del-Pozo, S. García-Linares, M. Ferrer, V. Guallar, *Nat. Catal.* **2023**, 6, 1174-1185.